

PLY -ANGLE VARIATIONS DUE TO PEEK SHEAR PLASTICITY IN APC2 COMPOSITE LAMINATES

F. TOUCHARD*, M.C. LAFARIE-FRENOT**, D. GAMBY**,
D. GUEDRA-DEGEORGES*

* Centre de recherches Louis Blériot, AEROSPATIALE, 92152 Suresnes Cedex, France.

**Laboratoire de Mécanique et de Physique des Matériaux, ENSMA, 86034 Poitiers Cedex, France

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is the extension of a semi-analytical model including elasticity, plasticity and damage to predict the mechanical behaviour of APC-2 (AS4 carbon fibre, PEEK thermoplastic matrix) laminates. Tests consisting of quasi-static uniaxial tension with successive loadings and unloadings are performed. It is shown that in $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates large angle variations between fibre direction and loading axis on one hand and important residual stresses due to plasticity on the other appear. This effect has to be taken into account to determine the model parameters more accurately. Predicted and experimental tensile stress-strain curves are compared for different lay-ups in T300/914 and APC-2 composites. In its original form the model appears better adapted to thermoset composites.

Keywords : carbon fibre/thermoplastic matrix, composites, laminates, damage, modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the aerospace industry, large amounts of thermoset CFRP are used ; for such composites, failure under mechanical loading may result from the development and accumulation of various damage modes [1]. The development of reliable tools for the analysis and prediction of these phenomena is necessary in order to optimize the use of these materials. Kachanov and Rabotnov proposed to use the variations of the Hooke tensor as a damage indicator. This idea has been developed by Lemaître and Chaboche [2] and taken over for anisotropic materials by Ladeveze [3].

For thermoset composites, some analytical models based on this theory with damage elastic parameters have already been proposed and assessed [4], [5]. On the other hand, thermoplastic matrix systems, such as APC-2 material (AS4 carbon fibre, PEEK matrix), are now developed for increasing toughness and damage tolerance. The mechanical behaviour of these composites is affected by the important ductility of the matrix [6].

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

Terminology for laminate and ply axes used in this paper is defined in figure 1.

The model is based on the constitutive mechanical equations of an elementary ply of a fibrous composite laminate. Continuum damage mechanics is used to describe the loss of stiffness of the elementary ply and plasticity is taken into account through isotropic strain hardening. By an homogenization technique, the stress-strain curves of any laminate subjected to a tensile loading can be predicted up to failure.

Figure 1. Terminology used in this paper.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of a loading-unloading stress-strain curve.

This model has been implemented in a numerical code named "DAMLAM" [7][8]. The mechanical behaviour of the elementary ply is characterized by the following parameters :

- the initial elastic moduli ($E_{11}^0, E_{22}^0, G_{12}^0, \nu_{12}^0$).
- the ultimate stress in fibre direction : σ_{11}^R . The behaviour in fibre direction is assumed to be linear elastic till failure.
- the growth law of two scalar damage variables with applied stress :

$$\text{for shear behaviour : } d = 1 - \frac{G_{12}}{G_{12}^0}$$

$$\text{for transverse tensile behaviour : } d' = 1 - \frac{E_{22}}{E_{22}^0}$$

Damage master curves involve a quantity Y_m [4], which plays the role of a strain energy release rate.

- the plasticity master curve.
- the failure criterion is based either on instability ($\dot{\sigma} = 0$ for $\dot{\epsilon} \neq 0$) or on fibre fracture, or on maximal Y_m value.

3. MODEL IDENTIFICATION

3.1. Loading-unloading tensile tests

Quasistatic tensile tests with a constant crosshead displacement rate (1 mm/min) are performed at room temperature on 230 mm x 20 mm laminate coupons. Longitudinal and transverse in-plane strains (ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{yy}) are measured using strain gauges. For the identification procedure, $[0]_8$, $[45]_8$ and $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminates are tested. Several unloadings allow to obtain stiffness values at different stress levels (figure 2). Two other laminates are tested in order to check the model predictions : $[\pm 30]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 60]_{2s}$. In situ X-ray photographs have been taken during loading-unloading tensile tests in order to observe crack growth and to measure the angle θ between fibre direction (visualized by crack direction) and loading axis. Tests on $[0]_8$ coupons confirm the linear elastic behaviour of APC-2 composite in fibre direction.

3.2. Theoretical analysis

For the model identification the aim is to determine for each laminate used the ply quantities : $\epsilon_{ij}, \sigma_{ij}$ ($i, j = 1, 2$) from the measured quantities : σ_{xx} (laminate average stress), ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{yy} (in-plane strains).

3.2.1. Study of a [45]8 laminate

X-ray photographs on [45]8 APC-2 laminates show that the fibre direction ($\theta = 45^\circ$) remains constant up to the ultimate stress. Moreover, the ultimate strains are less than 10 %. So, the classical equations using the small strain assumption, $\theta = 45^\circ$ and ϵ_{11} smaller than ϵ_{22} and ϵ_{12} are applicable :

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{2} & \epsilon_{11} &\simeq 0 \\ \sigma_{22} &= \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{2} & \epsilon_{22} &= \epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy} \\ \sigma_{12} &= \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{2} & \epsilon_{12} &= \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_{xx} - \epsilon_{yy})\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

3.2.2. Study of a $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ laminate

It has been shown in a previous paper [9] that fibre direction in $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminates decreased from 45° to 33° during tensile tests. Cervenka observed a similar magnitude phenomenon [10]. It is thus necessary to take into account angle variations when determining ply characteristics.

Equations for a $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ laminate with initial angle θ_0 :

- determination of the angle θ with the small strain assumption :

$$\cos 2\theta = \cos 2\theta_0 + 2(\epsilon_{xx} \cos^2\theta_0 - \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2\theta_0) \quad (2)$$

- determination of strains ϵ_{ij} :

hypotheses : small strains and plate theory.

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{11} &= \epsilon_{xx} \cos^2\theta + \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2\theta \\ \epsilon_{22} &= \epsilon_{xx} \sin^2\theta + \epsilon_{yy} \cos^2\theta \\ \epsilon_{12} &= (\epsilon_{xx} - \epsilon_{yy}) \sin\theta \cos\theta\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

- determination of stresses σ_{ij} :

additional hypothesis : linear elastic behaviour in fibre direction.

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= \frac{E_{11}}{1+\nu_{12}} \left(\epsilon_{xx} \cos^2\theta + \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2\theta + \nu_{12} \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{E_{11}} \right) \\ \sigma_{22} &= \frac{1}{1+\nu_{12}} \left(\sigma_{xx} - E_{11} (\epsilon_{xx} \cos^2\theta + \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2\theta) \right) \\ \sigma_{12} &= \frac{1}{\sin 2\theta} \left(\sigma_{xx} - \sigma_{11} \cos^2\theta - \sigma_{22} \sin^2\theta \right)\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

If the angle θ is considered constant and equal to 45° , the above equations for $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates reduce to [4] [7] :

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{11} &= \frac{E_{11}}{1+\nu_{12}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_{xx}}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_{yy}}{2} + \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \sigma_{xx} \right) & \epsilon_{11} &= \frac{1}{2} (\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) \\ \sigma_{22} &= \frac{1}{1+\nu_{12}} \left(\sigma_{xx} - E_{11} \left(\frac{\epsilon_{xx}}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_{yy}}{2} \right) \right) & \epsilon_{22} &= \frac{1}{2} (\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) \\ \sigma_{12} &= \frac{\sigma_{xx}}{2} & \epsilon_{12} &= \frac{1}{2} (\epsilon_{xx} - \epsilon_{yy})\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

However, in the case of a very ductile material such as APC-2 composite, these equations are no more valid because of the large variations of fibre direction. So, the model identification for $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 lay-ups must use the equations (2), (3) and (4).

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Small strain assumption

The small strain assumption (valid when $\epsilon_{ij} < 10\%$) is applicable up to failure for all the laminates investigated except $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ lay-ups. For $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ coupons, it is applicable only up to $\sigma_{xx} = 225$ MPa.

3.3.2. Influence of angle variation

θ variation has a very important influence on the ply characteristics for $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminates. For example figure 3 shows the variations of ϵ_{22} with σ_{xx} obtained by considering either θ constant or θ variable. It appears that, early in the test, the negative ϵ_{22} values determined with θ variable are larger than the same quantities determined with θ constant.

Figure 3. Ply strain ϵ_{22} versus applied stress σ_{xx} for $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminate : comparison between calculations with constant and variable angle.

3.3.3. Residual stresses

Figure 4. Schematic representation of ply stress-strain curve with residual stresses due to plasticity.

Large amount of residual stresses due to plasticity has been observed in the unloaded $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminate. For example, it can be seen in table 1 that, after loading up to $\sigma_{xx}^{max} = 220$ MPa, the residual stresses obtained in the unloaded specimen are more than half the maximal stresses.

Table 1. Maximum and residual stress values in a unidirectional ply of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 lay-up in the small strains range.

σ_{xx}^{max} MPa		26	48	112	142	188	220
σ_{11}^{max} MPa		54	108	284	385	467	774
σ_{11}^{res} MPa		0	10	24	190	230	477
σ_{22}^{max} MPa		-28	-60	-172	-243	-279	-554
σ_{22}^{res} MPa		0	-10	-24	-190	-230	-477
σ_{12}^{max} MPa		13	24	52	56	43	-24
σ_{12}^{res} MPa		0	0	0	-5	-23	-79

When the applied average stress σ_{xx} is zero, stresses in each ply have not vanished. Matrix plasticity prevents the laminate from recovering its initial configuration : in particular the fibre angle does not go back to 45° when the laminate is unloaded. Because of these residual stresses, a new form of stress-strain curves is obtained (Figure 4).

3.3.4. Plastic strains

The only plastic strain value required for model identification is ϵ_{12}^P which can be approximatively obtained by extrapolation of the unloading value to $\sigma_{12} = 0$ (figure 4).

3.4. Master curves

3.4.1. Transverse tension damage

The transverse modulus has been measured with tests on APC-2 laminates. The modulus E_{22} decreases with increasing applied stress (figure 5), leading to a quasi linear master curve $d' = f(Y_m)$ with a small damage threshold value (figure 6).

Figure 5. Transverse modulus versus applied stress for APC-2 composite.

Figure 6. Master curve of transverse tension damage for APC-2 composite.

3.4.2. Shear damage

Shear behaviour is determined with tests on $[45]_8$ and $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates. For $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ lay-ups, calculations have been performed according to two methods :

- using the classical equations (5) with a constant fibre angle,
- using the equations (2), (3) and (4) with a variable fibre angle.

Figure 7. Shear modulus versus applied stress for APC-2 composite.

Figure 8. Master curve of shear damage for APC-2 composite.

It is observed that the shear modulus G_{12} importantly decreases as the applied stress increases and tends to zero when σ_{xx} is higher than 225 MPa, the upper limit of the small strain range. Calculations with classical equations give much too high values for G_{12} (figure 7). The master curve $d = f(Y_m)$ obtained by taking into account the angle variation can be considered linear with a very low damage threshold value (figure 8).

3.4.3. Plasticity behaviour

The plasticity master curve has been obtained using classical equations on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminates. The strain hardening is represented in the form :

$$R = \beta p^\alpha \quad \text{with :} \quad \begin{array}{l} R : \text{the radius of the loading surface} \\ p : \text{cumulative shear plastic strain} \\ \beta, \alpha : \text{constants} \end{array}$$

Studies are in progress for taking into account the angle variation in the plasticity master curve.

4. NUMERICAL PREDICTIONS

In the present model, the unidirectional ply behaviour is described by means of thirteen parameters. The numerical code "DAMLAM", using classical equations with a constant fibre angle, is used in order to predict the tensile behaviour of some T300/914 and APC-2 laminates.

4.1. T300/914

The "DAMLAM" code has been checked for T300/914 laminates [7] [8]. The tests we made on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ T300/914 lay-ups show that fibre direction is almost constant up to failure. The brittle behaviour of the thermoset matrix does not allow fibre reorientation. Hence, classical equations are still valid for the T300/914 material. This explains that predicted and experimental tensile curves for different T300/914 lay-ups are in good agreement (figure 9 and table 2).

Figure 9. Comparison between prediction and test for $[\pm 60]_{2s}$ T300/914 laminate.

4.2. APC-2

The comparison between predicted and experimental tensile curves for different APC-2 laminates (figures 10 and 11) shows that :

- there is a good agreement for the beginning of the curves,
- predicted failure is always too early (table 2).

This last observation might be related to above mentioned remarks concerning fibre reorientation and plasticity behaviour.

Figure 10. Comparison between predicted and experimental stress-strain curve for $[\pm 30]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminate.

Figure 11. Comparison between predicted and experimental stress-strain curve for $[\pm 60]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminate.

Table 2. Comparison between predicted and experimental ultimate stresses.

Material	APC-2					T300/914		
	[0] _g	[45] _g	[+45] _{2s}	[+30] _{2s}	[+60] _{2s}	[+45] _{2s}	[+30] _{2s}	[+60] _{2s}
σ_{xx}^R test MPa	2154 ± 52	129 ± 13	376 ± 6	750 ± 38	110 ± 2	181 ± 3	435 ± 17	83 ± 3
σ_{xx}^R prediction MPa	2100	95	133	348	90	175	481	88

5. CONCLUSION

Loading-unloading tensile tests and in situ X-ray photographs have been performed on different APC-2 laminates. Large angle variations between fibre direction and loading axis in $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 lay-ups have been observed. The study of the influence of fibre re-orientation on ply characteristics has shown that important residual stresses due to plasticity appear in $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ APC-2 laminate. This has been taken into account to determine damage parameters required for a semi-analytical model based on elasticity, plasticity and damage theory. Comparison between predicted and experimental tensile stress-strain curves for several T300/914 and APC-2 laminates shows that the model in its original form is less efficient for the APC-2 material. Some alterations in the model appear necessary in order to take into account angle variations in predicted behaviour calculations. A more accurate determination of the plasticity master curve is also in progress.

References

- Williams, J.G., *Fracture mechanics of composites failure*, Proc. Instn. Mech. Engrs. vol. 204, pp. 209-218, Twenty-sixth John player lecture 1990.
- Lemaitre, J., Chaboche, J.L., *Aspect phénoménologique de la rupture par endommagement*, J. de mécanique appliquée, Vol.2, n° 3, pp. 315-365, 1978.
- Ladevèze, P., *Sur la mécanique de l'endommagement des composites*, 5^e Journées Nationales sur les Composites, 9-11 Sept. 1986, pp. 667-683.
- Le Dantec, E., Engrand, D., Perret, L., *Damage mechanics modelisation in industrial design*, European Conference on New advances in Computational structural mechanics, April 2-5, 1991, pp. 221-228.
- Kamimura, K., *Modélisation théorique de la croissance d'endommagement appliquée à la théorie des plaques stratifiées*, Journal de Mécanique théorique et appliquée, vol. 4, n° 4, 1985, pp. 537-553.
- Cottenot, C., Vautey, P., Marais, C., Sigety, P., *Comportement et endommagement comparés des composites carbone à matrices thermo-durcissable et thermoplastique*, Annales des Composites, 1989, 1/2, pp. 145-155.
- Le Dantec, E., Ladevèze, P., *Damage modelling of the elementary ply for laminated composites*, Composites Science and Technology, 43 (1992), pp.257-267.
- Bahlouli, N., Le Dantec, E., Perret, L., *Application de la mécanique de l'endommagement des matériaux composites stratifiés dans un contexte industriel*, 8^e Journées Nationales sur les Composites, 16-18 Nov. 1992, pp. 605-616.
- Touchard, F., *In plane shear behaviour of carbon-PEEK composite*, Advanced Composites Letters, vol. 1, n° 3, 1992, pp.113-115.
- Cervenka, A., Sheard, P., *Mechanical behaviour of angle-ply PEEK/Carbon fiber laminates : theory/experiment correlation*. Polymer Composites, June 1992, vol. 13, n° 3, pp. 149-153.